

MECHANICAL & RHEOLOGICAL BEHAVIOR OF HDPE-BASED POLY (ETHYLENE-CO-METHACRYLIC ACID) NANOCOMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

In order to prepare HDPE-montmorillonites nanocomposites, two ionomers, poly (ethylene-co-methacrylic acid), were used as compatibilizers. First, ionomers/HDPE blends were prepared using an internal mixer. The effect of ionomers on HDPE rheological and mechanical properties was significant. Then, clay's dispersion into ionomers was controlled and the impact of the compatibilizers on dispersion was observed.

Keywords: Nanocomposite, polyethylene, ionomer, poly (ethylene-co-methacrylic acid), Young's modulus, montmorillonite, complex viscosity.

HEADINGS

Since pioneer works carried out around fifteen years ago, several industrial fields have taken interest in nanocomposites based on organo-modified clays. Contrary to other polymers, the addition of compatibilizing agents is needed in order to disperse the organo-modified clays in polyolefin matrices. Polyolefin grafted maleic anhydride has been frequently used as compatibilizing agent [1-3]. Recently, ionomers were also reported as possible compatibilizers for polyolefins [4-6]. They are a type of random copolymer with a tiny percentage of side acid groups, a fraction of which is neutralized by a metallic counter-ion.

This work is focused on the preparation of HDPE-montmorillonites nanocomposites using different ionomers. The first part focuses on the impact of ionomers on rheological and mechanical properties of HDPE. Then, the effect of ionomers on organo-modified clay's dispersion is studied.

Materials

High density Polyethylene (Metallocene M4707) was purchased from TOTAL Petrochemicals. Two poly (ethylene-co-methacrylic acid), named respectively P2 and P3, were used as compatibilizers. They show rates of 19 and 15 wt% of acid function and partially neutralized with sodium cations. Purified Na-montmorillonite (Na-MMT) and commercial organo-modified montmorillonites, Nanofil2[®] (Nano2) and

Cloisite30B[®] (C30B), modified respectively with dimethyl-stearyl-benzyl ammonium and diethyl-hydroxyl-methyl-stearyl ammonium were used.

Processing

A HAAKE RHEOMIX[®] 300 internal mixer with two counter-rotating rollers was used for the preparation of nanocomposites at a clay percentage of 5 wt%. The processing temperature was set at 180°C. The rotating speed of the rotor and the mixing time were respectively, 60 rpm and 10 min. Dumbbell specimens were produced at 180 °C using a Sandretto Otto 95 injection molding device.

Characterization methods

Morphologies were analyzed using a Bruker D8 diffractometer using Cu K α radiation. Data were collected between 1 and 13° by a step size of 0.02° using an X-ray generator with $\lambda = 0.15406$ nm. Transmission Electron Microscopic microphotographs were obtained using a JEOL 1200EX2 apparatus with an acceleration voltage of 120 kV. Samples were 70 nm thick and prepared with a Leica Ultracut UCT ultra-microtome. Scanning Electron Microscopy microphotographs were also obtained using an environmental microscope Philips FEI.

One millimeter-thick samples were analyzed using a Rheometric Scientific (ARES[®]) equipped with parallel plates. Each sample was analyzed at 180°C in a frequency range from 10⁻¹ to 10² Hz.

Mechanical testing was performed using a ZWICK Z010 tensile test apparatus, at 20 °C at a constant rate of 1 mm/min for Young's modulus determinations, according to the ISO 527-1 standard.

Results and discussion

1. Rheological behavior of HDPE/ionomers blends

HDPE/Ionomer blends were prepared by an internal mixer at different weight percentage of ionomer (5, 10, 15, 20 and 25 wt %). Complex viscosity of both ionomers, P2 and P3, is slightly different. It seems to be controlled by the weight percentage function of each material (Fig.1).

At low frequencies, viscosity of HDPE/Ionomer blends increased by raising the ionomer percentage. It seems to be controlled by the polar character of the compatibilizing agents (Fig.2 and 3). The highest zero shear viscosity values correspond to the more polar ionomer (Fig.4). Furthermore, this viscosity seems be linear dependent on the ionomer percentage until 20 wt% and then levels off. This could be explained by the polar character of the blend. From to 20 wt%, the zero shear viscosity was the same for both systems which could be explained by a saturation of the miscibility phase of the ionomer on the HDPE matrix.

Fig.1: Complex viscosity of virgin matrix.

Fig.2: Complex viscosity of HDPE/P2.

Fig.3: Complex viscosity of HDPE/P3.

Fig.4: Zero shear viscosity of HDPE/Ionomer blends.

The presence of two distinct phases in the HDPE/ionomer blends was confirmed by rheological measurements and observations using scanning electronic microscopy. If one phase was formed, G' vs. G'' master curves would be obtained. Fig.5 shows that it is not the case, which could prove that more than one phase was formed.

Fig.5: G' vs. G'' for HDPE/Ionomer blends.

2. Morphologies of HDPE/ionomer blends

Fig.6 presents the SEM images of fracture surface for HDPE/Ionomer blends with various blend ratios. All samples present typical two phases. The dispersed phase clearly shows an elongated or fibrous structure. This fibrous phase appears generally oriented, probably as a consequence of shear flow during the injection mould filling. As expected, the size of the dispersed structures increases as the ionomer content in the blend increases. Moreover, this fibrous structure shows an inter-connected network between each other. Fig.7 shows SEM analytic characterization of the whole structure in order to determine more clearly the number of phases. The chemical composition corresponding to the network structure is only carbon, oxygen and sodium proving so that the edge of this fibrous structure is formed by complex carboxylate structure of ionomer (Tetracoordinated link [8]). For the rest of the blend, no sodium was detected proving that this phase is composed by carboxylic acid and HDPE.

Fig.6: SEM micrographs of HDPE/P3 blends: (a) 5 wt%, (b) 10 wt%, (c) 15 wt%, (d) 20 wt%, (e) 25 wt%.

Fig.7: Chemical characterization of HDPE/Ionomer phases (20 wt% of ionomer).

3. Mechanical properties of HDPE/Ionomers

Significant effects on the mechanical properties of HDPE due to the influence of ionomer addition were noticed. A decrease of Young's modulus was observed by increasing the ionomer percentage (Fig.8). This is ascribed to the plasticizing effect of short chains grafted on the backbone of the compatibilizing agents. The effect is more noticed with P3 ionomer than P2 one because of the lower modulus of P3 compared to P2.

Fig.8: Young's modulus of HDPE/ionomer blends.

4. Morphologies of ionomers/montmorillonites

XRD measurements for ionomers/clay have shown a decrease in the interlamellar spacing (18 to 14Å) when 5 wt% organo-modified clays were incorporated in the ionomers. This phenomenon cannot be ascribed to a degradation of the alkyl ammonium as mentioned in previous works [7], owing to the low values of processing temperatures. The C30B was used to determine if possible interactions between ionomers acid group and clay hydroxyl group could occur. However, a decrease in the interlamellar spacing was also shown.

Another explanation could be given for this phenomenon. The carboxylic groups ($\text{COO}^- \text{H}^+$) and the neutralized acid groups ($\text{COO}^- \text{Na}^+$) of the ionomer may interact with ammonium cations inside the interlayer galleries removing part or totally of them from the galleries. Finally, a partially protonated or sodium cationic exchanged clay with a collapse of interlayer space is obtained as observed in XRD (Fig.9). This hypothesis will be verified in the end of this work.

Fig.9: Possible way to explain the decrease of interlayer distance.

The effect of temperature on the dispersion was also studied (Fig.10). A weak increase of the interlayer distance was observed (14 to 16Å). It may be due to some ionomer tetracoordinated structure which changed to simple carboxylate function due to heat and thereafter could react with clay.

Fig.10: Effect of temperature on interlayer distance of ionomers/clays blends.

Then, dispersion analysis of organo-modified clays in the ionomers was controlled by rheological measurements at 180°C. The incorporation of clay nanoparticles in the ionomers resulted in a Newtonian behavior at low frequencies revealing the absence of network between nanoparticles and ionomers (Fig.11). Natural montmorillonite seems more dispersed in ionomer matrix compared to organo-modified clay due to interactions between ionomers and sodium cations present in the montmorillonite.

Fig.11: Complex viscosity of P2/Clay blends compared to virgin sodium ionomer.

The absence of interaction between nanoparticles and ionomers seems prove that the organo-clays, due to cations present in the backbone of ionomer, were changed from organo-modified montmorillonites to non organo-modified ones. In order to verify this hypothesis, the ionomer will be modified with alkyl ammonium and natural clay will be used to find out if there is intercalation.

P2 ionomer was modified by a trimethyl hexadecyl ammonium bromide. First, ionomer was solubilized into THF at 80°C. Then, 20 wt% of the alkyl ammonium was added. The modification lasted 12h. Finally, modified ionomer was dried under vacuum for 24h. Then, a blend was made in an internal mixer at 160°C with 5 wt% of natural montmorillonite dried also at 80°C. The result is given by Fig.12.

The interlayer distance of natural montmorillonite dried at 80°C is 9.8 Å. After dispersion in the modified ionomer, four peaks were shown at $2\theta=2.25, 4.5, 6.7$ and 8.9° (Fig.12). These correspond to an interlamellar distance of 41, 20.5, 13.35 and 10.2 Å. We can notice that the two first numbers are multiples. Indeed, it corresponds to the same intercalation peak with $n=1$ and $n=2$ (Bragg law, $n\lambda=2d\sin\theta$). The third peak corresponds to a natural montmorillonite blended with interlayer sodium cations. This is may be due to sodium cations still not modified in the ionomer. Some natural montmorillonite remains not dispersed in the modified ionomer. It is shown by the final pick at 8.9° . This result was confirmed by TEM (Fig.13). Consequently, our hypothesis seems to be verified. Indeed, due to cations present in the ionomer, dispersion of organo-modified montmorillonite in sodium ionomer is limited. Nevertheless, in

presence of modified ionomer with an alkyl ammonium, natural montmorillonite had been dispersed.

Fig.12: X-ray scattering of MMt-Na^+ dried at 80°C and MMt-Na^+ dispersed in the modified ionomer.

Fig.13: TEM micrographs of modified ionomer/ MMt-Na^+ .

Conclusion

This work has been shown that the effect of ionomer on mechanical and rheological properties of HDPE is considerable. A complex phase structure was formed and attributed to the polar character of ionomer which generated poor interfacial adhesion with the non polar HDPE. A decrease of Young's modulus was also shown and it has been ascribed to the plastizing effect of the short acid chains grafted on the backbone of

the compatibilizing agents. A slightly increase of the complex viscosity of the HDPE can be due to the polarity of the ionomer.

Dispersion of organo-modified montmorillonite in sodium ionomer seems partially achieved. No network was formed between nanoparticles and ionomer referring to rheological measurements. This could be explained by the sodium counter-ion which interacts with ammonium cations inside the interlayer galleries removing part or totally of them from the galleries. Partially or totally protonated or sodium cationic exchanged clay with a collapse of interlayer space is obtained. This hypothesis seems verified by neutralizing sodium cations of the ionomer by an alkyl ammonium and blending with a natural montmorillonite.

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